

IMMUNOLOGICAL STATUS OF YELLOW IN INFANTS

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Abstract: Jaundice in newborns is a physiological or pathological condition, which manifests itself in the first week of the child's life with hyperbilirubinemia in the blood and yellowing of skin color and visible mucous membranes. This article provides information on the causes, prevention and immunological conditions of jaundice in newborns.

Key words: Hyperbilirubinemia, hemolytic disease, neonatology, bilirubin, phototherapy.

Hyperbilirubinemia (jaundice) is a high level of bilirubin in the blood and a clinical manifestation of jaundice. Hyperbilirubinemia in babies, that is, jaundice, should be taken seriously. The reason is that if the amount of bilirubin in the blood increases, it can damage the brain and cause serious functional disorders. Often this disease develops without symptoms. The general condition of the child will be good. There are no changes in the liver and spleen. The baby's urine and stool tests may also be normal. In some cases, this disease damages the central nervous system with symptoms such as drowsiness and loss of appetite. In healthy newborns, symptoms of jaundice disappear by the second and third weeks of life.

Physiological jaundice can be observed in babies born on time from 3-4 to 14 days, and in premature babies up to 24 days. The first signs of jaundice appear in a newborn baby for 24-36 hours. Therefore, it is necessary to take seriously any jaundice that appears in the first days of a baby's life, and to immediately examine and treat the child.

Jaundice is a yellowing of the skin and the whites of the eyes. The yellow color is caused by bilirubin, a byproduct of the breakdown of old red blood cells, which, after being "recycled" by the liver, is excreted with bile and passed out of the body in the stool. This normal process can be disturbed for a number of reasons, high levels of bilirubin lead to jaundice in babies. In addition to jaundice, the baby sometimes has trouble sleeping or feeding, and the color of the urine is darker.

In this regard, the first task of a neonatologist - a doctor - is to determine the sign of jaundice, whether it is physiological or pathological jaundice. For this, one of the most important tasks is to determine the mother's diseases, blood analysis, history of family diseases, blood group of the child's parents.

The form of manifestation of jaundice in a baby is in a certain sequence. It is necessary to correctly determine the speed of jaundice and the rate of increase. It helps in many ways to distinguish physiological jaundice from pathological jaundice.

If jaundice is observed in different parts of the baby's body on the first day of life, and on the palms and heels on the second day of life, phototherapy is immediately performed under the supervision of a doctor.

If the child is given timely and necessary help, these signs can pass. However, if timely help is not provided, in severe cases of the disease, a high level of bilirubin can damage the brain of a newborn baby. As a result, it can cause jaundice, which can lead to disability and even death of the patient.

Causes of jaundice

Physiological jaundice in infants is caused by the inability of the immature liver to process and excrete bilirubin. Usually on the second or third day, you can see that the baby's face and whites of the eyes have turned yellow. Jaundice starts on the head/face of a newborn baby, and if the level increases, jaundice can also be seen on the body and limbs. If the baby's face is yellow, the bilirubin level will be much lower than if the body and legs are yellow.

Jaundice of breast milk occurs due to the presence of inhibitory substances in milk that temporarily disrupt the metabolism and excretion of bilirubin. It usually occurs a few days after birth, although it can last for several weeks, it is harmless to the baby and will go away on its own. It is not necessary to stop breastfeeding during this time and it is not recommended to do so!

Jaundice (hemolytic disease of the newborn) caused by blood type incompatibility of the mother and baby is accompanied by other laboratory findings and requires treatment.

Less common causes of jaundice include infection in the newborn, inborn errors of metabolism, or biliary tract defects. These are serious but fortunately very rare cases. Neonatal jaundice is sometimes confused with infectious hepatitis, which is mostly caused by viruses and is very rare in newborns.

Measurement of bilirubin. Bilirubin is measured in the newborn's serum or skin. Although transcutaneous measurement has some limitations, it is a painless and convenient measurement method for infants and provides reliable results in children who have not received phototherapy. If the readings are significantly higher or the child has other symptoms, additional laboratory tests are performed.

If jaundice is physiological, why is it treated?

Although jaundice in newborns is often caused by physiological factors, sometimes the rates are so high that it poses a great risk to the newborn and requires treatment. Phototherapy effectively reduces bilirubin levels and is safe for newborns. If the bilirubin level is very high and is accompanied by other disorders, the appropriate treatment is used.

Prevention of jaundice

Breastfeeding is a very important preventive measure! Mother's milk not only provides the newborn with enough fluid and energy, but also accelerates the process of "recycling" bilirubin in the liver due to its content. Colostrum stimulates bowel movements and the absorption of beneficial probiotic bacteria in the gut, which prevents jaundice. Giving water or glucose solution to a non-dehydrated newborn does not prevent or relieve jaundice. Never leave your baby in direct sunlight! Sunlight is not effective in treating jaundice, but can be harmful and dangerous for the delicate skin of a newborn baby.

Etiology. In an adult, erythrocytes are constantly renewed, old cells are metabolized to produce bilirubin, which is excreted by the liver. Since the baby's liver is not yet fully functional, bilirubin produced during the replacement of fetal hemoglobin gives a yellow color to the skin and mucous membranes from the third day of life. When the body's enzyme systems begin to function fully, the child's skin color will return to its normal state, i.e. its light pink color. Jaundice is usually most pronounced on the third or fourth day of life and usually disappears by 7-8 days of life[1].

Treatment:

The need for treatment depends on the level of bilirubin, the maturity level of the child and the underlying cause of the jaundice.

Treatment is carried out with frequent feeding, phototherapy. Premature babies require more intensive treatment.

A child's 1-month bilirubin norm is up to 45 $\mu\text{mol/l}$.

Phototherapy

Indications for the appointment of phototherapy vary depending on the specific level of bilirubin, the level of maturity, the health of the newborn and the age of the child. However, any neonate younger than 14 days with a plasma total bilirubin greater than 220 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (21 mg/dL) should receive phototherapy.

Neonatal jaundice in newborns can be treated with light, which converts trans-bilirubin to the water-soluble cis-bilirubin isomer, which is better excreted in the urine and feces.

The phototherapy used is blue light of a certain frequency, not UV light therapy. During the procedure, the child's eyes should be tightly closed.

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